

followIT – a wrist position annotation tool

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Abstract: To address the problem of occlusion in hand tracking, this work presents the software followIT as an annotation tool in which the positions of wrists are manually annotated by users in previously recorded 3D point clouds. These are captured by the Microsoft® Azure Kinect Depth Camera. The software is developed with Python and is based on Open3D. The result is a csv-file including the coordinates for each wrist to generate trajectories. The evaluation shows that followIT enables the user to estimate visible and occluded wrists nearly as good as ground truth tools.

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I. Introduction

More and more, robots are making their way into healthcare. They support professionals in their specific activities and can potentially take over care activities, especially physically demanding tasks such as patient repositionings. For learning processes robots often rely on trajectories of sample activities. In healthcare and nursing, especially the caregivers' hands are an important tool that must be tracked. Due to the usually close physical contact between nurses and patients during the interactions, the hands are often not visible for optical tracking in video sequences. Therefore, they cannot be automatically recognized and tracked using image processing techniques. To address this problem, this work presents the software *followIT* as an annotation tool in which the spatial positions of wrists are manually estimated and annotated in generated point clouds by users.

I.1. Requirements

To digitalize nursing movements, it is necessary to be able to process initially recorded RGB-Depth video sequences (hereafter RGB-D video sequences) of these movements. Additionally, the use of 3D data is mandatory to generate 3D coordinates for the trajectories of these movements and to be able to use it for training tasks in real world. As occlusions are unavoidable during nursing tasks the system has to be capable of tracking fully occluded wrists to generate a complete path of movement. And lastly, the tracking of more than one wrist is essential because nursing tasks often require at least two hands.

I.2. Related Works

Occlusion is a problem for optical tracking systems and is rarely considered in present systems. A study by István Sárándi et al. [1] shows that the performance of state-of-the-art benchmarks for pose estimation quickly decreases for increasing occlusion.

In an approach using 3D data a “pre-computed motion database” is created by Mao Ye et al. [3] to compare an input point cloud with the database and thereby estimate the

body configuration in the input point cloud. But this approach does not consider occlusions, is not appropriate for RGB-D video sequences and for the analysis of more than one person.

A third approach addresses the tracking of hand-object-interactions by classifying the hand and the object, clustering them into regions and using 3D Gaussian Mixture Models for the pose estimation of the hand [2]. But the hand is not fully occluded and only one hand is recorded.

In the evaluated research papers and literature no approach fulfills all the aforementioned requirements (1.1).

II. Material and methods

The annotation tool *followIT* is developed with Python 3.7.4. The data processing is implemented with Open3D [4] which provides the common processing algorithms for 3D data and an integrated visualization of the data. To make the interaction more intuitively, GUIs are developed with PyQt5.15.2.

Figure 1: Process pipeline of the annotation process with followIT

followIT supports the whole process from preprocessing of data to the resulting trajectory representing the path of movement of the observed wrist (Fig. 1). Firstly, RGB-D video sequences are recorded with one Microsoft® Azure Kinect (hereafter Azure Kinect) with the Azure Kinect Sensor SDK v1.2.0 to get 3D data of the scene. The video files are saved as mkv-files. In the preprocessing stage the videos are split into frames: for each frame one RGB image as jpg-file and one depth image as png-file are created. Afterwards point clouds are generated from each pair of RGB and depth images and are stored in a directory as pcd-files.

Figure 2: Annotated wrist

To start the annotation process, the point cloud directory is selected, a csv-file is created and the wrist that is to be annotated is selected. For each point cloud the annotated x-, y-, and z-coordinates are stored in this csv-file. By clicking *start*, the visualizer of Open3D is opened and the first point cloud with the index 0 is displayed. In this visualizer the specified wrist is annotated manually. Therefore, a three-dimensional coordinate frame is inserted in the visualizer by pressing the insert key. It can be shifted to the wrist's position by using the q-w-e-a-s-d-keys on the keyboard: q- and e-key to move into and out of the plane, w- and s-key for up and down, and a- and d-key for left- and rightwards. The appropriate position (Fig. 2) of the coordinate frame on the wrist is confirmed by pressing the return key. Thereby, the coordinates of this position are written into the csv-file in the corresponding row. In the next point cloud the coordinate frame is inserted where it was confirmed in the previous one. This process from inserting the coordinate frame to confirming its position will be repeated for all point clouds of the dataset.

The marked position in a point cloud can be corrected at any time if it turns out that it does not fit at all. Therefore, the coordinate frame can be shifted with the aforesaid keys and the new position is confirmed by pressing the return key again. The new coordinates override the coordinates in the csv-file in the respective row of this point cloud.

For linear movements a linear interpolation algorithm is implemented to facilitate the annotation. Therefore, the wrist is annotated in a point cloud and is confirmed with the return key. Then some point clouds are skipped and in the subsequent point cloud the wrist is annotated again. Here the position is confirmed by pressing the i-key. Thereby, the wrist's position is interpolated over the skipped point clouds and all positions are stored in the csv-file.

The coordinate frames for the annotations do not remain in the point clouds when the visualizer is closed; only their positions are saved. So, the same dataset can be reused.

The csv-file represents the results and can be used in the learning process of nursing movements for robots or staff in healthcare.

III. Results and discussion

The *followIT* annotation tool was evaluated with the TEA's Captiv motion capture suit (hereafter Captiv). Therefore, a video was recorded with the Azure Kinect. The subject (me) wearing the inertial measuring units (IMUs) of the Captiv was standing 2 m away from the camera, which was mounted on a tripod at 1.135 m height. Simultaneously to the video recording the Captiv recorded the coordinates of the wrists. These measured coordinates were also stored in

another csv-file. Finally, the video was processed in the *followIT* annotation tool as described in section II.

As both tools use different coordinate systems as reference, the reference system of the Azure Kinect used in the annotation tool, too, was transformed into the coordinate system used by the Captiv. As the origin of Captiv's coordinate system lies in the ground beneath the fifth lumbar vertebra it was not possible to determine the translation factors exactly. To evaluate the performance of *followIT* nevertheless, the pathways of the discrete measuring points were compared. To quantify these observations the correlation coefficient was determined for each axis: For x (representing the movement left- and rightwards) we get a correlation coefficient of 0.9316, for y (back and forth) 0.4048, and for z (up and down) 0.8888. According to the correlation coefficients of x and z close to 1 the manually annotated coordinates are very similar to the ground truth data measured by the Captiv. Only the coefficient for y does not yield a good result which is due to an extrinsic calibration error. This requires further research.

For a more reliable result on the performance of *followIT*, more datasets and more diverse motion sequences should be annotated and evaluated.

IV. Conclusions

To our knowledge the *followIT* annotation tool is the first tool that makes it possible to manually annotate every wrist regardless of whether it is visible, partially occluded, or fully occluded. It can process RGB-D video sequences by using the preprocessing stage and it is able to process 3D data by using the Open3D API. By only saving the coordinates the same dataset can be reused without any modification and thus enables the annotation of more than one wrist – sequentially. With this method it is also possible to track wrists of more than one person by creating a new csv-file for every person. As the evaluation shows, *followIT* enables the user to estimate visible and occluded wrists nearly as good as ground truth tools.

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